

SELECTION RESPONSE AND CORRELATION STUDIES FOR METRICAL TRAITS IN
MUTANT CARNATION (*Dianthus caryophyllus* L.) GENOTYPES

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ABSTRACT

The present study was conducted to evaluate mutant Carnation (*Dianthus caryophyllus*) genotypes to assess the magnitude of genetic variability and to pick up the heritable component of variation for selection response of metrical traits. Mean data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) that revealed highly significant differences for all the characters studied and set up of a correlation matrix to analyze the stability capability by critical difference (CD) values and effect of mutagens for character improvement. Total number of leaves/plant was most stable due to its higher CD value; weight of 1000 seeds was highly variable with lower stability. It has been confirmed that 0.4% dose of all three mutagens was highly effective than other doses. The phenotypic and genotypic co-efficient of variation (PCV & GCV) value shows the influence of the environmental effect on the characters. Highest GCV and PCV were noticed for total branches/plant and lowest for total flowers per plant. Heritability ranged from 46.77 (Days to seed germination) to 96.09 (Plant height at 50% flowering phase) per cent. Total number of leaves and branches showed high, seeds per inflorescence and days to branching showed moderate and plant height at 50% flowering showed low genetic advance with higher heritability. Thus, these traits may serve as an effective selection parameter and screening of promising mutant line (s) for crop improvement.

Key words: Character selection; chemical mutagen; *Dianthus caryophyllus*; genetic variability; metrical trait.

INTRODUCTION

Carnation (*Dianthus caryophyllus* L.), belongs to the angiospermic family Caryophyllaceae, is an important floricultural crop all over the world and ranks just next to Rose in popularity in western countries (Laurie *et al.*, 1968; Staby *et al.*, 1978). It grows very well in temperate climate, specially in Eurasia. This genus is important by having pharmacological properties, aromatic things and polymorphism in morphology, genetics and hybridization (Facciola, 1990; Hughes, 1993; McGeorge and Hammett, 2002; Su Yeons, 2002; Lee *et al.*, 2005). In this modern era, an agronomic demand of high yielding cultivar of this crop was noticed. Mutation can produce the development of *Dianthus* cultivars with more desirable floral characteristics and higher productivity (Roychowdhury and Tah, 2011a; Roychowdhury, 2011). Inducible mutation, using chemical or physical mutagens, is a suitable source of producing variation in crop improvement through mutation breeding (Domingo *et al.*, 2007) which can produce several improved mutant varieties with high economic value (Din *et al.*, 2004). From applicational point of view, it is quite possible to induce gene-mutation artificially with the help of some potent chemical mutagens like N-nitroso Methyl Urea (NMU), Ethyl Methane Sulphonate (EMS), Sodium Azide (SA), etc. to create any new variation in this crop. The mutation breeding performance in *Dianthus* species can significantly accelerate many breeding endeavors, which have proven difficult with classical *Dianthus* breeding techniques (Roychowdhury, 2011). Various metrical attributes like seed weight, number of branches, leaves, flowers, leaf area, etc., are very much complex in nature because it is governed by polygenes and greatly influenced by environmental factors. It is a powerful and effective tool in the hands of plant breeders especially for autogamous crops having narrow genetic base (Micke, 1988). The success of any breeding program depends to a large extent on the amount of genetic variability present in the population. Wide spectrum of genetic variability has been induced in Carnation (*Dianthus caryophyllus* L.) using both physical and chemical mutagens in order to utilize it in floricultural improvement and inheritance studies (Patil, 1966; Ashri, 1970; Gowda *et al.*, 1996). Overall variability must be partitioned into heritable and non- heritable components with the aid of genetic parameters such as genotypic and phenotypic coefficients of variation, heritability and genetic advance (Ariyo, 1987; Roychowdhury and Tah, 2011b). Genetic variability studies provide basic information regarding the genetic properties of the population based on which breeding methods are formulated

for further improvement of the crop. These studies are also helpful to know about the nature and extent of variability that can be attributed to different causes, sensitive nature of the crop to environmental influences, heritability of the characters and genetic advance that can be realized in practical breeding. Progress in any crop improvement venture depends mainly on the magnitude of genetic variability and heritability present in the source material. The extent of variability is measured by genotypic coefficient of variance (GCV) and phenotypic coefficient of variance (PCV) which provides information about relative amount of variation in different characters. Hence, to have a thorough comprehensive idea, it is necessary to have an analytical assessment of metrical components. Since heritability is also influenced by environment, the information on heritability alone may not help in pin pointing characters enforcing selection. Nevertheless, the heritability estimates in conjunction with the predicted genetic advance will be more reliable (Johnson *et al.*, 1955). Heritability gives the information on the magnitude of inheritance of quantitative traits, while genetic advance will be helpful in formulating suitable selection procedures. The present study permits an effective screening of large plant population leading to generate demanding mutant lines. Therefore, an attempt was made in this investigation to estimate the extent of various genetic parameters like variability, heritability and genetic advance in nine Carnation treatments (both normal and mutagen treated) for some common agronomically important metrical traits and establishing a suitable breeding procedure, except expensive available molecular breeding methods along with developing a high quality and better yielding new Carnation germplasm to increase its diversity and sustainable agro-economical market demand by analyzing the stability capability and effect of mutagens for character improvement.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

To conduct the present study, pure line seeds of *Dianthus caryophyllus* were collected from Globe Nursery, Kolkata and treated with three potent chemical mutagens viz. N-nitroso methyl urea (NMU), Ethyl methane sulphonate (EMS) and Sodium azide (SA) according to Roychowdhury and Tah (2011c) using three different doses like 0.1% (w/v), 0.4% (w/v) and 0.7% (w/v) for each mutagen. The treated seeds were then washed in running tap water to remove the chemical present in them and placed in absorbent cotton-wet petridish for recording the germination behaviour. The germinated seeds were finally transferred to experimental plots. The mutagen treated seeds were sown for raising first mutant (M_1) generation in the well manured experimental field of Crop Research Farm (latitude 23.53° N, 22.56° S and longitude 83.25° E, 86° W) under Botany Department, The University of Burdwan, West Bengal, India, during winter season (2009). Ten randomly selected M_1 plants per treatment along with control were tagged, harvested individually and viable seeds were stored in a desiccator for proper restoring. The second mutant (M_2) generation was grown from single plant M_1 Subscript progeny seeds. They were raised in the next winter season (2010). This sowing process for raising M_2 progeny was done separately, depending upon the concentration of chemicals with proper marking and followed Randomized Block Design (RBD) layout with three replications for each treatment. Each treatment was sown in three rows of 4 m length plot and 25 cm apart by adopting the spacing of 25 x 25 cm. Normal recommended cultural practices and plant protection measures were followed to raising M_2 generation. Uniform agronomical measures were provided for this M_2 crop in the field experimentation. The data were recorded on five randomly selected plants from each replication in M_2 generation for some metrical traits studied viz. days to seed germination, plant height (cm) at 50% flowering phase, days to branching, total number of branches per plant, total leaves per plant, leaf area (cm²), total number of flower per plant, diameter of flower (cm), number of seeds per inflorescence, weight (g) of 1000 seeds. The all data were analyzed statistically. Mean values were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) to test the significance for each character, as per methodology advocated by Panse and Sukhatme (1957, 1967), which employed to obtain, assemble, classify and to interpret voluminous quantitative data that might have been influenced by many external environmental factors. The mean characters that showed significant variations were used to determine partial correlation and simple linear correlation coefficients according to Snedecor and Cochran (1967). A correlation matrix was drawn up using the linear correlation coefficients. Phenotypic and genotypic variances were estimated according to the formula given by Lush (1940). The genotypic and phenotypic coefficients of variation (GCV and PCV) were worked out according to the method given by Singh and Chaudhary (1985). Heritability in broad sense was worked out according to the method given by Allard (1960). Expected Genetic Advance (GA) of the genotypes and its per cent of mean at 5% intensity of selection pressure (2.06 after Kang *et al.*, 1983) were calculated according to Singh and Chaudhary (1985). New codes were given to each mutagenic treatment such as: Control= ST₁, 0.1% NMU=ST₂, 0.4% NMU= ST₃, 0.7% NMU= ST₄, 0.1% EMS=ST₅, 0.4% EMS=ST₆, 0.7% EMS=ST₇, 0.1% SA=ST₈, 0.4% SA=ST₉, 0.7% SA=ST₁₀.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this experiment, any progeny from the seeds treated by 0.7 % SA (ST₁₀) was not obtained due to lethal effect of respective mutagenic dose combined with low germinability of seeds. The recorded mean values in five randomly selected plant samples for different agro-economically important metrical attributes have been presented in Table 1. Days to seed germination ranged between 4.03 (ST₃) - 5.82 (ST₉), where control (ST₁) showed 4.67. Plant height (cm) at 50% flowering phase and days to branching have a range between 45.87 (ST₉) - 54.8 (ST₃) and 15 (ST₉) - 21 (ST₂), respectively; whereas control plant showed the value 48.73 and 16.67 for respective traits. The ranges 3.33 (ST₆) - 6.32 (ST₄), 36.2 (ST₆) - 84.2 (ST₃) and 27.2 (ST₂) - 42.3 (ST₃) were for number of branches per plant, total leaves per plant and number of flower per plant, respectively. Leaf area range from 3.25 (ST₄) to 4.5 (ST₃) in which control (ST₁) and ST₉ share the same value 3.35. In case of flower diameter and seeds/inflorescence, the range were 3.87 (ST₇) - 4.4 (control and ST₃) and 22.6 (ST₇) - 33.3 (ST₃), respectively. Control has a value 28.6 for the later. Weight of 1000 seeds ranged from 1.35 (ST₃) to 1.63 (ST₅ and ST₆), where control showed 1.59, i.e., very much close to the highest range. In the treatments, increase in NMU concentration gear up the plant height, days to branching, branches/plant, total leaves/plant, leaf area, number of flowers/plant (especially at 0.4% NMU) and reduced flower diameter, 1000 seed's weight and also delayed seed germination, when compared with control plant. Same effects for those characters were observed in three different concentrations of EMS, which were somewhat reversed in SA treatment. Action of SA on *Dianthus* was proved to increase days to branching, branches/plant, no. of seeds/inflorescence and weight of 1000 seeds, while to decrease plant height, leaf area, days to seed germination, total leaves/plant, total flowers/plant and flower diameter. For their similarity, the numbers of flower, length of petal and seed weight are to be considered. So, SA treatment negatively affected for these traits. Here, NMU treatments have a greater potential than control plants. Best performance was shown by 0.4% NMU (ST₃) among its three different concentrations for improving the concerned traits. Effect of EMS and SA were below the performance of control plant to some extent, but EMS treatment produce better quantitative value than the SA treatment. EMS at 0.4% (ST₆) and 0.4% SA (ST₉) treatment gave the better result than their other doses. These analyses will require further exercise for its stable confirmation and screening of promising mutant line (s) in M₂ and subsequent generations.

The results in Table 2 indicate that branches per plant (BP), total number of leaves per plant (LP) and number of flower per plant (FP) correlated positively and significantly at 5% probability ($P < 0.05$) with plant height at 50% flowering phase (PH), while seeds per inflorescence (SI) and weight of 1000 seeds (WS) showed negatively correlation with plant height (PH). Similarly, there were positive and significant relationship between number of branches per plant (BP) and days to branching (DB), where $r = 0.604$ at $P < 0.05$; total leaves per plant (LP) and total number of branches per plant (BP), where $r = 0.836$ at $P < 0.01$. Partial correlation was significant at 5% probability ($P < 0.05$) for plant height at 50% flowering phase and number of branches per plant and also at 1% probability ($P < 0.01$) for only total leaves per plant, which are clearly shown in Table 3. This means that plant height, number of branches per plant and total leaves per plant contributed over 63% to some extent in various metrical attributes. Other characters were not significant, of which days to seed germination, leaf area and flower diameter showed negative partial correlation value. In t-test for significance, plant height and total leaves per plant were significant at $P < 0.01$, while significant at $P < 0.05$ was confirmed by days to branching, number of branches per plant and total number of flowers per plant.

The mean values of aforesaid agro-metrical characters were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) to confirm the differences among *Dianthus* cultivar which were treated by different concentrations of three potent chemical mutagens. Mean squares from analysis of variance of ten indicated metrical traits of *Dianthus caryophyllus* are presented in Table 4. The table depicted highly significant differences among mutagenic treatments for all the studied characters. This indicates that there is huge scope for selection of promising mutant lines with different quantitative and qualitative traits from the present gene pool. The presence of wide range of variability might be due to diverse source of materials after mutation taken as well as environmental influence affecting the phenotypes. The value of variance ratio was as calculated significant at 1% level in case of plant height at 50% flowering phase, days to branching, total branches per plant, total leaves per plant, number of flowers per plant, flower diameter and seeds per inflorescence and at 5% level in the resting traits, i.e., days to

seed germination, leaf area and weight of 1000 seeds. The coefficient of variation (CV) and critical difference values (CD) were also calculated in all these ten metrical traits. Highest CV value was governed by leaf area (13.262); moderate range was 6.686 – 8.926 where days to seed germination showed 8.926, weight of 1000 seeds showed 7.953 and 6.686 for days to branching. Plant height at 50% flowering phase represented lowest CV value ranging from 1.437 – 4.214. In this range, the CV of total flowers per plant, number of leaves per plant and flower diameter was 3.119, 3.132 and 4.214, respectively. Total leaves per plant showed highest CD value (4.49). Moderate range of CD was 1.43 – 2.74, where days to branching, seeds per inflorescence, flowers per plant, plant height and branches per plant having the value 2.74, 2.64, 1.96, 1.73 and 1.43, respectively. Lowest CD governed by weight of 1000 seeds (0.21). Flower diameter (0.41), days to seed germination (0.66) and leaf area (0.88) also occupy in the lower range of CD value, i.e., 0.21 – 0.88. Higher the CD value corresponds to higher stability of respective character in the prevailing environmental conditions (Roychowdhury and Tah, 2011a). Total number of leaves per plant was most stable due to its higher CD value. Days to branching, number of seeds per inflorescence, total flowers per plant, plant height and total branches per plant were moderately stable and varied to some extent. Weight of 1000 seeds was highly variable with lower stability. It is evident from table 4 that significant F value has been found in all characters. It is nothing but due to the plantation of cultivars in proper seasonal time and also positive environmental effects. The significant CD values indicate that *Dianthus* cultivar is no doubt suitable in the location where prevailing agro-climatic factors were favourable for plantation of this crop. The fluctuations of various characters were varied from treatment to treatment. There were lots of minute variations during growth and developmental phases in the field condition. It is due to the easy penetrance power of used three chemicals in form of liquid solution (Roychowdhury, 2011; Roychowdhury and Tah, 2011a).

The estimates of genetic parameters like genotypic (σ^2_g) and phenotypic (σ^2_p) variance, genotypic (GCV) and phenotypic (PCV) coefficient of variation, broad sense heritability (h^2_{bs}) and genetic advance (GA) for different carnation genotypes are presented in Table 5. A perusal of Table 5 reveals that the mean values for all the characters showed sufficient high differences among the genotypes. The differences among maximum and minimum values of all characters were high in total leaves per plant (48.0), total flowers per plant (15.1) and number of seeds per inflorescence (10.7). The other characters showed non-significant differences. The maximum genotypic and phenotypic variation were obtained for total leaves per plant (27.10, 29.93) and seeds per inflorescence (25.49, 29.61), while moderate variation was observed for plant height (11.326, 1.787), days to branching (4.9, 5.97) and total no. of flower per plant (3.56, 5.14). This indicated that the environment did not influence these characters very much. Values of phenotypic and genotypic variance were very close for weight (g) of 1000 seeds (0.104, 0.155) and flower diameter (0.105, 0.195). The character with almost nearest value of phenotypic and genotypic variance can be considered as stable (Yadav *et al.* 2010). Lower values of genotypic and phenotypic variance were noticed in days to seed germination, leaf area, flower diameter and 1000 seed weight, which is indicative of the stable nature of these characters. Similar findings were reported by Ganesan *et al.* (1994) and Rao *et al.* (1996).

In general, phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV) was higher in magnitude than the genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV) for all the characters studied, the close resemblance between the corresponding estimates of both PCV and GCV in almost all the characters suggested that the environment had little effect in those characters expression (Jalgaonkar *et al.*, 1990). The GCV provides a measure to compare genetic variability present in various quantitative characters. The highest value of it was recorded for total branches per plant (0.75), moderate for seeds per inflorescence (0.561) and days to branching (0.439); lowest for total flowers per plant (0.179) and flower diameter (0.195). The higher value clearly indicated high degree of genotypic variability in these quantitative traits in *Dianthus caryophyllus*. PCV which measure total relative variation was highest for total branches per plant (0.882); moderate for seeds per inflorescence (0.638), leaf area (0.613), days to branching (0.505) and seed germination (0.406); lowest for total no. of flowers per plant (0.214) and for plant height (0.246). Similar result was reported by Pathania *et al.* (1988). High values of GCV suggest better improvement scope for these traits by selection. However, the estimation of heritable variation with the help of genetic coefficient of variation alone may be misleading. Burton (1951, 1952) suggested that the genetic coefficient of variation together with heritability estimates gave the better picture of the extent of heritable variation. Heritability (h^2) and genetic advance (GA) estimates were interpreted as low medium and high as per the classification of Johnson *et al.* (1955). Broad sense heritability (h^2_{bs}) ranged from 46.77 (Days to seed germination) to 96.09 (Plant height at 50% flowering phase) per cent. High heritability was recorded for plant

height (96.09%), no. of branches per plant (92.98%) and total leaves per plant (90.54%); moderate heritability for seeds per inflorescence (86.09%), days to branching (82.07%), leaf area (70.35%), total flowers per plant (69.26%) and weight of 1000 seeds (67.10%); lowest for days to seed germination (46.77%) and flower diameter (53.85%). High heritability combined with high genetic advance as per cent of mean (GAM) was observed for total leaves per plant and total no. of branches per plant. This indicates the lesser influence of environment in expression of these attributes and prevalence of additive gene action in their inheritance, hence amenable for simple selection (Panse, 1957). High heritability with moderate genetic advance as per cent of mean was recorded for seeds per inflorescence and days to branching indicating that these characters were governed by additive gene interaction. High heritability coupled with low genetic advance as per cent of mean was recorded for plant height at 50% flowering indicating non-additive gene action for these traits.

CONCLUSION

The knowledge on heritability of traits is helpful in deciding the selection procedure to improve the trait given. Higher estimates of heritability with genetic advance as per cent of mean (GAM) was observed for total leaves per plant and total no. of branches per plant indicating the presence of additive gene action and so selection can be easily done for these traits. The trait i.e., plant height at 50% flowering, which expressed high heritability and low genetic advance showed non additive gene interaction, hence heterosis breeding would be recommended for that trait.

REFERENCES

- Allard, R.W., (1960), Principles of Plant Breeding. John Wiley and Sons, New York. 89-98 p.
- Ariyo, O.J., (1987), Variation and Heritability of Fifteen Characters in Okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L.). *Tropical Agric.*, 45: 67 – 71.
- Ashri, A., (1970), A dominant mutation with variable penetrance and expressivity induced by diethyl sulfate in peanuts (*Arachis hypogaea* Linn). *Mutation Res.*, 9: 473-480.
- Burton, G.W., (1951), Quantitative inheritance in Pearl millet (*P. glaucum*). *Agron. J.*, 43: 409-417.
- Burton, G.W., (1952), Quantitative inheritance in grasses. *6th Int. Grassland Congress*, 1: 277-283.
- Din, R., Qasim, M. and Ahmad, K., (2004), Radio sensitivity of various wheat genotypes in M₁ generation. *Int. J. Agri. Biol.*, 6: 898-900.
- Domingo, C., Andres, F. and Talon, M., (2007), Rice cv. Bahia mutagenized population: a new resource for rice breeding in the Mediterranean basin. *Spain J. Agric. Res.*, 5: 341-347.
- Facciola, S., (1990), Cornucopia: A Source Book of Edible Plants. Kampong Publications, California. 678 p.
- Galet, N., Mohammed, H. and Zelleke, H., (2005), Genetic variability and genetic advance in sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L. Moench) germplasm. *Crop Res.*, 30: 439-445.
- Gowda, M.V.C., Nadaf H.L. and Sheshagiri, R., (1996), The role of mutation in intraspecific differentiation of groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.). *Euphytica*, 90: 105-113.
- Ganesan, K., (1994), Genetic studies in F₂ and F₃ of tall x dwarf rice crosses. *Madras Agric. J.*, 81: 30-32.
- Hughes, S., (1993), Carnations and Pinks. The Crowood Press, Marlborough, UK.
- Jabeen, N., Ahmed N. and Tanki, M.I., (1998), Genetic variability in hot pepper (*Capsicum annum* L.). *Agric. Sci. Digest.*, 18: 23-26.
- Jalgaonkar, R., Jamadagni, B.M. and Salvi, M.J., (1990), Genetic variability and correlation studies in turmeric. *Ind. Cocoa, Arecanut and Spices J.*, 15 (1): 20-22.

- Johnson, H.W., Robinson, H.F. and Comstock, R.E., (1955), Estimation of genetic and environmental variability in Soybean. *Agron. J.*, 47: 314-318.
- Kang, M.S., Mille, J.D. and Tai, P.Y.P., (1983), Genetic and phenotypic path analysis and heritability in sugarcane. *Crop Sci.*, 23: 643-647.
- Laurie, A., Kiplinger, D.C. and Nelson, K.S., (1968), Commercial Flower Forcing (7th Ed.). McGraw-Hill Book Company, New York. 72-76, 94, 96, 105,116, 117, 284, 285 p.
- Lee, S.Y., Yae, B.W. and Kim, K.S., (2005), Segregation patterns of several morphological characters and RAPD markers in interspecific hybrids between *Dianthus giganteus* and *D. carthusianorum*. *Sci. Hort.*, 105: 53-64.
- Lush, J.L., (1940), Intra - sire correlation and regression of offspring on dams as a method of estimating heritability of characters. *Proc. Amer. Soc. Animal Production*, 33: 293-301.
- McGeorge, P. and Hammett, K., (2002), Carnations and Pinks. David Bateman Ltd., Auckland. 1-96 p.
- Micke, A., (1988), Genetic improvement of grain legumes using induced mutations: An overview. In: Improvement of Grain Legume Production Using Induced Mutations. IAEA, Vienna. 1-51 p.
- Munshi, A.D. and Behera, T.K., (2000), Genetic variability, heritability and genetic advance for some traits in chillies (*Capsicum annuum* L.). *Vegetable Sci.*, 27: 39 – 41.
- Nayak, A.R., Chaudhary, D. and Reddy, J.N., (2002), Genetic variability, heritability and genetic advance in scented Rice. *Indian Agriculturist*, 46: 45-47.
- Panse, V.G., (1957), Genetics of quantitative characters in relation to Plant Breeding. *Ind. J. Genet. & Plant Breed.*, 17: 318-328.
- Panse, V.G. and Sukhatme, P.V., (1967), Statistical Methods for Agricultural Workers (2nd Ed.). ICAR publication, New Delhi. 381 p.
- Pathania, N., Singh, M. and Arya, P.S., (1988), Genetic evaluation of some economic traits in turmeric (*Curcuma longa* L.). *Himachal J. of Agri. Res.*, 14 (1): 38-43.
- Patil, S.H., (1966), Mutations induced in groundnut by X-rays. *Ind. J. Genet.*, 26A: 334-348.
- Rao, T.P., Gomathinayagam, P. and Soundrapandian, S., (1996), Genetic variability and character association studies in semi-dry rice. *Madras Agri. J.*, 83(3): 185-188.
- Roychowdhury, R., (2011), Effect of Chemical Mutagens on Carnation (*Dianthus caryophyllus* L.): A Mutation Breeding Approach (1st Ed.). LAP Lambert Academic Publishing, Germany. 14 p.
- Roychowdhury, R. and Tah, J., (2011a), Mutation breeding in *Dianthus caryophyllus* for economic traits. *Elec. J. Plant Breed.*, 2(2): 282-286.
- Roychowdhury, R. and Tah, J., (2011b), Evaluation of Genetic Parameters for Agro-metrical characters in Carnation Genotypes. *Afr. Crop Sci. J.*, 19 (3): 183 -188.
- Roychowdhury, R. and Tah, J., (2011c), Chemical mutagenic action on seed germination and related agro-metrical traits in M₁ *Dianthus* generation. *Current Bot.*, 2(8): 19-23.
- Singh, R.K. and Chaudhary, B.D., (1985), Biometrical Methods in Quantitative Genetic Analysis. Kalyani Publishers, Ludhiana. 318 p.

Staby, G.L., Robertson, J.L., Kiplinger, D.C. and Conover, C.A., (1978), Chain of Life. Ohio Florist's Association, Ohio State University, Columbus.

Snedecor, G.W. and Cochran, W.G., (1967), Statistical Methods (6th Ed.). Iowa State University Press, USA. 456 p.

Su Yeons, K., (2002), Genetic relationship among Korean *Dianthus* species based on morphological characteristics and RAPD Analysis.

Yadav, P., Rangare, N.R., Anurag, P.J. and Chaurasia, A.K., (2010), Quantitative analysis of Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) in Allahabad agro-climate zone. *J. Rice Res.*, 3(1): 16-18.

Table 1: Mean value of five randomly selected plants of *Dianthus* cultivar from each treatment for agronomic traits.

TR	CC (%)	DS	PH	DB	BP	LP	LA	FP	DF	SI	WS
Control	---	4.67	48.73	16.67	3.64	56.3	3.35	37.9	4.4	28.6	1.59
NMU	0.1	5.10	54.40	21	6.2	72.4	4.34	27.2	4.25	23.8	1.6
	0.4	4.03	54.80	15.33	5.67	84.2	4.5	42.3	4.4	33.3	1.35
	0.7	4.69	52.60	19.24	6.32	82.7	3.25	38.3	4.0	28.3	1.45
EMS	0.1	4.33	46.9	15.67	4.35	42.3	4.36	34.6	3.9	31.6	1.63
	0.4	4.27	50.27	15.41	3.33	36.2	3.92	36.3	4.0	27.5	1.63
	0.7	4.53	53.43	19	4.66	52.3	3.65	39.7	3.87	22.6	1.52
SA	0.1	4.70	48.3	17	4.31	64.4	3.76	41.6	4.1	24.8	1.49
	0.4	5.82	45.87	15	4.66	51.76	3.35	31.4	3.9	31.9	1.58

TR=treatment, CC=Concentration, NMU= N-nitroso methyl urea, EMS= Ethyl methane sulphonate, SA= Sodium azide, DS=days to seed germination, PH=plant height (cm) at 50% flowering phase, DB=days to branching, BP=total number of branches per plant, LP=total leaves per plant, LA=leaf area (cm²), FP=total no. of flower per plant, DF=diameter of flower (cm), SI=seeds per inflorescence, WS=weight (g) of 1000 seeds.

Table 2: Correlation matrix between selected important metrical traits in both control and chemical mutagen treated *Dianthus caryophyllus*. '*' and '**' sign indicate the significant at 5% and 1% probability, respectively. Abbreviation of characters are DS=days to seed germination, PH=plant height (cm) at 50% flowering phase, DB=days to branching, BP=total number of branches per plant, LP=total leaves per plant, LA=leaf area (cm²), FP=total no. of flower per plant, DF=diameter of flower (cm), SI=seeds per inflorescence, WS=weight (g) of 1000 seeds.

	DS	PH	DB	BP	LP	LA	FP	DF	SI	WS
DS	1									
PH	-0.394	1								
DB	0.149	0.598	1							
BP	0.148	0.626*	0.604*	1						
LP	-0.035	0.623*	0.429	0.836**	1					
LA	-0.480	0.346	-0.058	0.179	0.072	1				
FP	-0.638	0.742*	-0.289	-0.191	0.209	-0.111	1			
DF	-0.246	0.380	0.043	0.150	0.529	0.265	0.155	1		
SI	-0.068	-0.335	-0.746	-0.019	0.047	0.148	0.074	0.142	1	
WS	0.319	-0.532	-0.025	-0.534	-0.800	-0.069	-0.669	-0.344	-0.194	1

Table 3: Partial correlation, linear regression coefficients t-test for significance of some selected important metrical traits in *Dianthus* cultivar after mutagenic treatment. '*' and '**' sign indicate the significant at 5% and 1% probability, respectively.

Metrical Traits	Partial Correlation	Linear Regression Coefficients	t-test for significance
Days to seed germination (DS)	-0.46	0.028	1.57
Plant height at 50% flowering phase (PH)	0.69*	0.305	6.13**
Days to branching (DB)	0.38	0.092	2.43*
Number of branches/plant (BP)	0.633*	0.157	2.84*
Total leaves/plant (LP)	0.73**	0.091	3.64**
Leaf area (LA)	-0.38	-0.063	1.27
Total no. of flower/plant (FP)	0.43	0.091	2.34*
Diameter of flower (DF)	-0.28	-0.053	1.43
Seeds/inflorescence (SI)	0.25	-0.58	1.56
Weight of 1000 seeds (WS)	0.18	0.062	1.39

Table 4: Analysis of variance for metrical characters in 9 treatments of *Dianthus caryophyllus* including control and mutant ones grown at Crop Research Farm, Burdwan University. Mean sum square (MSS) of replications, treatments and error along with critical difference (CD) and coefficient of variation (CV) were calculated for each studied characters. 'df' denotes degree of freedom.

Serial No.	Characters	Mean Sum Squares (MSS)			Coefficient of Variation (CV)	Critical Difference (CD)
		Replication [df=2]	Treatment [df=8]	Error [df=16]		
1.	Days to seed germination	0.12	0.48*	0.132	8.926	0.66
2.	Plant height (cm) at 50% flowering phase	0.369	34.44**	0.461	1.437	1.73
3.	Days to branching	1.482	15.78**	1.07	6.686	2.74
4.	Total no. of branches/plant	1.99	5.26**	0.129	12.535	1.43
5.	Total leaves/plant	1.74	114.13**	2.83	3.132	4.49
6.	Leaf area (cm ²)	0.09	0.96*	0.118	13.262	0.88
7.	Total no. of flower/plant	4.32	12.26**	1.58	3.119	1.96
8.	Diameter of flower (cm)	0.11	0.406**	0.09	4.214	0.41
9.	Seeds/inflorescence	1.273	80.59**	4.12	10.01	2.64
10.	Weight (g) of 1000 seeds	0.012	0.363*	0.051	7.953	0.21

* and ** sign indicate the significant at probability 5% and 1% level of significance, respectively

Table 5: Components of genetic variability for 10 metrical characters among normal and mutant genotypes of *D. caryophyllus* L.

Sl No.	Characters	Mean (X)	Range		Components of Variance			GCV	PCV	h ² _{bs} %	GA	GA as % of mean
			Max	Min	σ ² _g	σ ² _p	σ ² _e					
1.	Days to seed germination	4.93	5.82	4.03	0.116	0.248	0.132	0.235	0.406	46.77	0.239	4.85
2.	Plant height (cm) at 50% flowering phase	50.34	54.8	45.87	11.326	11.787	0.461	0.239	0.246	96.09	23.33	46.34
3.	Days to branching	18.0	21.0	15.0	4.9	5.97	1.07	0.439	0.505	82.07	10.09	56.05
4.	Total no. of branches/plant	4.83	6.32	3.33	1.71	1.839	0.129	0.750	0.882	92.98	3.52	72.88
5.	Total leaves/plant	60.2	84.2	36.2	27.10	29.93	2.83	0.359	0.377	90.54	55.82	92.72
6.	Leaf area (cm ²)	3.88	4.5	3.25	0.28	0.398	0.118	0.367	0.613	70.35	0.577	14.87
7.	Total no. of flower/plant	34.75	42.3	27.2	3.56	5.14	1.58	0.179	0.214	69.26	7.33	21.09
8.	Diameter of flower (cm)	4.14	4.4	3.87	0.105	0.195	0.09	0.195	0.254	53.85	0.216	5.22
9.	Seeds/inflorescence	27.95	33.3	22.6	25.49	29.61	4.12	0.561	0.638	86.09	52.51	87.87
10.	Weight (g) of 1000 seeds	1.49	1.63	1.35	0.104	0.155	0.051	0.253	0.388	67.10	0.214	14.36

σ²_g = genotypic variance, σ²_p = phenotypic variance, σ²_e = environmental variance, GCV = genotypic coefficient of variance, PCV = phenotypic coefficient of variance, h²_{bs} = heritability in broad sense, GA = genetic advance.

Received for Publication: 14/09/2011

Accepted for Publication: 30/11/2011

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